

HISTORY OF EMERGENCE AND DEVELOPMENT OF THE GAME IN EDUCATIONAL PROCESSES

Tursunkulova Makhfuza Tolkin qizi

Doctoral student of UzSRIPS

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***Abstract.** Didactic games have their place in lessons organized in school educational processes. It can be said that there is a history of the emergence and development of games. Based on this, this article is devoted to theories about the emergence and history of development of games in educational processes.*

***Keywords:** game, emergence of game, child, student, primary education, school students.*

In each field, there is a history of the emergence of a method or a tool, as well as stages of development. In addition, there is a history of the emergence and development of the game in educational processes. In these processes, it is even possible to observe the participation of world-famous pedagogic scientists.

Attempts to reveal the "secret" of the game's origin have been made by scientists from various fields of science for many centuries. The range of proposed ideas on the origin of the manifestation of the game is very wide and has already been considered in local philosophical and other scientific literature.

There are enough questions about the origin and motives of children's games, their structure and dynamics of development. There are also many important theoretical questions. Looking at the history of the game in order to find answers to these questions, we can witness the opinions and views of world scientists, pedagogues, and psychologists. Among them are the views of the American psychologist Schlossberg.

American psychologist Schlossberg pessimistically notes that the category of game activity is so vague that it is unbearable for modern science. It should be noted that most scientific concepts are characterized by the interpretation of play as a special "zone" of children of primary and preschool age. Although play is undoubtedly an important activity for teenagers, young adults, and adults, it generally accompanies a person throughout his or her life. The richness of the game element in any national culture can serve as one of the criteria for its humanitarian development.

O.S.Gazman, a researcher of schoolchildren's games, writes: "Nature created children's games for comprehensive preparation for life. Therefore, the game has a genetic connection with all types of human activity and works as a specific form of knowledge, work, communication, art, sports, etc. According to the enlightened people of the past, life is not interesting and boring for children without games. As S. T. Shatsky noted, the dullness of life causes something like a real disease in children. For this reason, it can be said that they save their lives from the darkness with the game.

There is hardly a person who has not heard and does not know about K.D. Ushinsky, one of the pedagogic scientists who left an indelible mark in the field of pedagogy and education. During his career, the scientist performed many useful actions for education and left a legacy for today's generations. As one of the most obvious aspects and actions of K. D. Ushinsky, it can be shown that he founded the theory of games in the system of Russian sciences.

K.D. Ushinsky (1824-1871) is the founder of game theory in Russian science. He contrasts the idea of using games in the general education system with the preaching of spontaneity with play activities. K. D. Ushinsky evaluates the activity of the child's movement in the game and puts forward the needs of the soul first: "We should not see in the child's physical movements only the satisfaction of bodily desires. The soul participates in these movements. And receives the same benefit from them for its development," he says. great Russian scientist.

The teacher sees that the mobility of the child is directly related to the mental and practical activity of his heart. Play is a whole world of practical activity for a child. Speaking against the pure hedonic (pleasure) theory of play, Ushinsky claims that children in the game seek not only pleasure, but also self-affirmation in interesting activities. According to Ushinsky, the game is a type of activity, moreover, it is a free and forced conscious activity that realizes the desire to live, feel, and act. "We must not forget," writes K.D. Ushinsky. The game in which the child's spirit works independently is also a child's activity. Ushinsky was one of the first to point out that aspiration, emotion, and representation are united at the same time in the game. Depriving a child of play as a conscious activity is the most terrible punishment for him.

In the theories of J. Piaget, K. Levin (1890-1947) - German-American psychologists, in the works of Russian psychologists V. Vygotsky, D. Elkonin, the modeling and orientation functions of the game are indicated as the child's ability to work with game symbols. These symbols replace unconditioned stimuli and serve as elements of culture for children.

D. Elkonin believed that by organizing activities with the help of symbols, the game teaches to move in the events of culture and spirituality in general, and to use them appropriately. Cultural scientist F. Ratsel also agreed with this opinion and noted that "people's games are a valuable evidence of their lifestyle and outlook on life." According to F. Ratzel, they are the ones who feed the game and encourage its appearance.

Shatsky, who believes that the appearance of the game "depends on the richness of the inner life that develops in the heart of the child", is in the same position. Many scientists, including Piaget, Levin, Vygotsky, Elkonin, Ushinsky, Makarenko, Sukhomlinsky, believed that the game appears in the light of spirituality and serves as a source of the child's spiritual development.

Scientists who lived in the Soviet era also expressed their thoughts and views about the game. One such scientist is the Soviet psychologist and philosopher S. L. Rubinstein.

Soviet psychologist and philosopher S. L. Rubinstein (1889-1960) was the first to try to create a local game theory. Rubinstein understands the game as a child's eternal need born of contact with the outside world, as a reaction to them. According to Rubinstein, the essence of the game is that it is a product of practice, through which the activity changes, the world changes: "The child's need to influence the world is formed and manifested in the game" . Therefore, it is a meaningful activity. According to Rubinstein, the motives of the game lie not in the utilitarian effect, but in various experiences that are important for the child due to the surrounding reality. The scientist proves that the child does not strive for a material result, but realizes various motives of human activity: "...actions in game activities are more expressive semantic actions than operational techniques," he admits.

The conclusions of Ushinsky and Rubinstein that the game is a meaningful activity were developed in the works of A.N. Leontiev. Leontiev considers the game to be the leading activity of a preschool child. He believes that play can only be explained in terms of its need for activity. In Leontiev's opinion: "The movement of the game is born from the need to act in relation to the

wider world." This is a secondary, reflected process of game development in the preschool period of a child's life. He, like Rubinstein, considered the game to be a type of objective activity and described it based on the characteristics of work in terms of goals, motives and methods of action. Leontiev has a great idea: "play is not a productive activity, its motive is not in the result, but in the action itself," he says. mastering a wider range of actions that cannot happen can only happen in play.

Thus, Rubinstein, Leontiev and their followers explained the game as a convenient way for the child to understand and master the world. So, from the point of view and opinions of scientists, it can be concluded that the uniqueness of game activity is manifested in unity with practical activity and therefore has an active, effective character. It should also be noted that in order to preserve the active and effective character of the game, it is very important to know at which stage didactic games can be used in educational processes and to be able to predict the result.

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